

1. Observations of some parts of the rice pistil using a light microscope. a) cross-section of a stigmatic hair, b) cross-section of a stigma, c) cross-section toward the bottom of an ovary, and d) longitudinal section of the dorsi-ventral direction of an ovary. Bars show 100 µm.

2. Observations of some parts of the rice pistil after pollination using an epifluorescence microscope. a) cross-section of stigmatic hair, b) longitudinal section of stigmatic hair, c) cross-section of the uppermost part of style, and d) cross-section of ovary. Bars show 100 µm.

Fluorescent microscopy showed that pollen germination occurred 1 h after the pollen reached the stigmatic hairs. The pollen tube then elongated, passing through the center hole of the stigmatic hair (Fig. 2a, b). In the stigmatic and stylar tissues, the pollen tube passed through the transmitting tissue located in the space between the center area and the vascular bundle (Fig. 2c). (Among Liliaceae species, the pollen tube is believed to pass through the stylar cavity.)

The cells comprising the transmitting tissue differed from other parenchymatous cells. They appear as a darkened area under the fluorescent microscope, implying that the cells were thin walls. The absence of a narrow space toward the dorsal side (downward) of the ovary explained the observation of pollen tube elongation at both sides of the locule but not in the dorsi-ventral direction of the ovary (Fig. 2d).

The pollen tube reached the micropyle 3 h after pollination. However, time of fertilization could not be determined. ■

Studies on intercellular space of embryo and seedling tissues in rice plants

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The development of intercellular spaces into aerenchyma in rice plants is thought to be important in improving oxygen gas diffusion through the plant body. But details of the developmental process during seedling and early vegetative stages are unclear. To better understand the process, a morphological study of intercellular spaces was conducted using high-resolution microscopy as well as cryo-scanning electron microscopy.

Intercellular spaces form in mature embryos of dry seeds (see figures a, b, c).

The spaces are located mainly in the parenchymatous cell regions including the scutellum, mesocotyl, and coleoptile and radicle, and are evident in the inner regions of these tissues. Intercellular spaces near the apical region of the radicle procortex were found in mature embryos, confirming previous findings (Armstrong 1979) (see figures f, g). However, all these spaces, which appear at the corner of neighboring cells, are very small in dry seeds. They increase in volume during imbibition and germination (see figures a-e).

During the early seedling stages after germination, no obvious changes in intercellular space were observed, but a tubular structure along the longitudinal cell alignment was formed (this occurred after the elongation and development of cortical cells along the shoot-root axis) (see figures e, f, h). In the shoot region, air space was formed in chlorenchymatous cell regions in the coleoptile and young leaves, especially under nonsubmerged culture condition.

The intercellular space near the axis during the early seedling stage seemed to be mostly in the water-rich state as revealed by cryo-scanning electron microscopy. Similar results have been obtained in other plants (Canny and Huang 1993). Seven days after germination, root air space was formed in the basal elongated seminal root region of the nonsubmerged plants. In the submerged condition, inner air space was formed among the elongated coleoptile and young leaves, while seminal root growth was reduced and the development of the cortical air space was delayed.

Cited references

- Armstrong W. 1979. Aeration in higher plants. *Adv. Bot. Res.* 7:225-332.
 Canny MJ, Huang CX. 1993. What is in the intercellular spaces of roots? Evidence from the cryo-analytical-scanning electron microscope. *Physiol. Plant.* 87:561-568. ■

Fertilizer management

Effects of time of split application of K on soil N forms and lowland rice yield

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An experiment was conducted to study the effect of timing of split application of K on N forms in the soil and on rice yield. The experiment was carried out using clay soil (Typic Chromusters. pH 8.04, electrical conductivity 0.32 dS m⁻¹, organic carbon 0.41 % and 294, 10, 290 kg available NPK ha⁻¹). The crop received 100-22-41.5 kg NPK ha⁻¹. Half of the N and K and the entire dose of P were applied basally. The remaining amount of N and K was equally split and topdressed as per treatment schedule (see table).

The experiment was carried out in two different seasons (February to June and July to November) using IR20 and a factorial completely randomized block design. Treatments were replicated thrice. Twelve replications were used (three replications at each stage of soil analysis).

Soil samples were taken at a depth of 15 cm during tillering, panicle initiation, flowering, and harvest stages. Wet soil samples were analyzed for NH₄-N, NO₃-N, available N, and fixed NH₄-N. Plants collected at harvest were threshed carefully to separate the grains and straw and weighed separately after drying at 60 °C.

In both seasons, grain and straw yields were highest when K was always applied 7 d earlier than N (see table). Yields were lowest in the control and when K was applied 7 d after N (see table). The higher grain and straw yield with early application of K was caused by the greater availability of NH₄-N and NO₃-N at tillering and panicle initiation (see figure),

Light micrographs of rice embryo tissues, showing intercellular spaces among the cells. A low magnification view of the radicle and mesocotyl regions of a mature embryo (a); higher profiles of the radicle procortex region (b); inner coleoptile cells (c) in dry seeds; inner scutellar parenchyma cells 48 h after imbibition (HAI) (d); meristematic cortical cell region of seminal root (e); and a lower view of the root (f), 72 HAI; apical region of the root tip, 96 HAI (g); and meristematic cells of the cortex, 120 HAI (h). d-h: nonsubmerged condition. Arrows indicate intercellular spaces. Bar = 50 μ m.